

Prompt-based Language Generation for Complex Conversational Coaching Tasks across Languages

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Abstract

We investigate the role of prompt-based demonstrators in improving natural language generation for coaching-oriented dialogue systems in different languages. These systems present significant challenges due to their need for semantically accurate, goal-driven responses across diverse dialogue act taxonomies and languages. We define three types of prompt demonstrators, i.e., pairs of meaning representation-utterance, that include different degrees of specification in such meaning representation. We then fine-tune pretrained language models separately for four very different languages and evaluate how the specificity of these demonstrators affects the quality of the generated sentences. Our experiments show that more specific prompts lead to more coherent and accurate outputs, particularly for low-resource languages and small models. Additionally, we observe promising zero-shot performance with larger models, showing a complementary value of prompts. These results demonstrate that simple prompting strategies, combined with fine-tuning, can significantly improve output quality in complex dialogue generation tasks across languages.

1 Introduction

Dialogue systems for coaching and healthcare applications must handle complex, user-centered interactions that go beyond giving or requesting information. These systems aim to support behavioral change through goal-oriented conversations, a challenge that requires high control and contextual awareness (Zhou et al., 2024; Carchiolo and Malgeri, 2024). Traditional rule-based systems fall short in flexibility, while Large Language Models (LLM)-based agents offer better adaptability but raise concerns about control and factual consistency, especially in sensitive domains like health (Carchiolo and Malgeri, 2024; Galland et al., 2024).

Table 1: EMPATHIC corpus characteristics per language.

Language	Corpus size	Running words	Vocabulary
English	1.2k	13.2k	1.7k
Spanish	1.1k	11.7k	2.0k
French	1.2k	13.0k	1.9K
Norwegian	1.1k	12.7k	1.7k

Recent work emphasizes the importance of pre-trained language models and prompt-based learning for improving generation in such scenarios (Algherairy and Ahmed, 2024). These methods allow models to generalize from a few examples using in-context learning, which is especially valuable when annotated data is limited or multilingual coverage is required (Zhou et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2023).

For goal-setting dialogues, even small variations in the input meaning representation (MR) can significantly affect the response’s quality and intent realization (Ramirez et al., 2023; Reed et al., 2022). Despite the wide research in prompt-based learning, the effects of some structural variations in the demonstrators are underexplored. In this work, we expand our research on how the similarity between MR inputs and demonstrators affects natural language generation in different domains (Vázquez and Torres, 2025) by introducing a cross-lingual perspective in a specific use case: complex dialogue systems in coaching contexts.

2 EMPATHIC task

The EMPATHIC project (Torres et al., 2019; Olaso et al., 2021; Vázquez et al., 2023) aimed to build a virtual coach that can assist users in changing their unhealthy habits, if any, through conversations. This virtual coach does not generally give advice or information. On the contrary, it follows the GROW model (Leach, 2020), a behavioral model that promotes users’ reflection with questions. Based on this model, the virtual coach first encourages the

Table 2: Examples of the EMPATHIC corpus in English.

MR	Sentence
GSQ_what_obj (action = change)	Would you like to change something in your habits?
RQ_curr_sit (numbers = five, food = fruits, food = vegetables)	Do you eat five fruits and vegetables a day?
Gen_Hello (user_name = Françoise)	Hello again, Françoise.
Gen_Agreement ()	That's true.

users to look for a **Goal**, making them aware of the possible weakness of their routines, in particular nutritional routines, by assessing their **Reality**. Next, the users explore their **Options** and **Will** to act, defining a plan for goals such as reducing the sugar/salt intake or a regular schedule for meals. Consequently, the EMPATHIC task implies higher complexity for a conversational system than traditional information providers (Wen et al., 2015; Novikova et al., 2017).

In this context, WoZ experiments (Justo et al., 2020) were carried out in Spanish, French, or Norwegian, the target languages of the project. In these experiments, a real user and a wizard, a person playing the role of the virtual coach, simulated a coaching session. These coaching sessions were transcribed and translated into English as well as into the three target languages. Therefore, the resulting EMPATHIC corpus¹ is a dataset with equivalent versions in four languages. Note that one of them is a low-resourced one: Norwegian. Table 1 shows a similar number of samples for the four languages. However, intrinsic differences between languages lead to different numbers of total words (running words) and vocabulary size.

Table 2 shows examples of coaching turns along with the MRs employed to annotate them. Questions promoted by the GROW model, such as "Would you like to change something in your habits?" or "Do you eat five fruits and vegetables a day?" resulted in domain-specific Dialog Acts (DAs) like GSQ_what_obj and RQ_curr_sit, respectively. GSQ and RQ, which stand for Goal Set Question and Reality Question, are two of the seven types of questions employed in the GROW model. Additionally, the EMPATHIC corpus also contains open-domain DAs like Gen_Hello for greetings or Gen_Agreement for agreement expressions. In total, 78 ad-hoc DAs were defined for the EMPATHIC corpus, a high number in comparison with other datasets such as E2E (Novikova et al., 2017) and ViGGO (Juraska et al., 2019) that employ one and nine DAs for 51k and 6.9k samples, respec-

tively. Finally, the MRs include attributes with their corresponding values found in each turn, such as food=fruits or action=change.

3 Meaning representations

Prior works (Vazquez et al., 2024; Ramirez et al., 2023; Reed et al., 2022) have shown that MRs, including an example of the task to perform in the input, i.e., a task demonstrator, generate more accurate and natural sentences. In this work, we aim to confirm the effectiveness of these kinds of representations for complex tasks, already demonstrated in English (Vázquez and Torres, 2025), across languages. Specifically, we consider three MRs with a demonstrator in the input, the Prompt representations. Then, we compare them with the original MR of the EMPATHIC corpus, the Baseline representation.

Table 3 shows a schema of the four representations. The baseline is just the Input MR found in the EMPATHIC corpus, while the prompts add a task demonstrator to this input. In consequence, the models generate sentences from the same MR in all the representations. For the prompts, the demonstrators are MR-sentence pairs consisting of a Demonstrator MR and a Demonstrator sentence, which are extracted from the corpus. And although these proposed inputs present the same format, they differ in their specificity, i.e., the similarity between the Demonstrator MR and the MR Input. The different levels of alignment between demonstrators and MR are indicated in Table 3 with colors, the letters n and m, and apostrophes. Same colors and letters indicate necessarily equal, while different colors and letters and apostrophes mean not necessarily equal. Therefore, the Demonstrator MR must have only the same DA as the Input MR for Prompt 1, the same DA and number of attributes for Prompt 2, and the same DA and attributes for Prompt 3.

Table 4 presents a real example of an MR of the English EMPATHIC corpus and its corresponding task demonstrator for each prompt. The DA of the three Demonstrator MRs and the Input MR is RQ_curr_sit, highlighted in blue in the table. The

¹Available at low cost on <https://catalog.elra.info/en-us/repository/browse/ELRA-S0414/>

Table 3: Meaning representations overview. Baseline includes only the Input MR (common for the four representations), whereas Prompt representations add a task demonstrator to the input. Same colour (bleu for DAs and red for attributes) in Task demonstrator and Input MR means necessarily identical. Similarly, letters n and m for the number of attributes are used to specify when this feature must necessarily be the same (or not). Finally, apostrophes in values, attributes, and demonstrator sentences (s, s' and s'') mean not necessarily equal.

Meaning representation	Task demonstrator	Input MR
Baseline	-	DA ($attr_1 = val_1, \dots, attr_n = val_n$)
Prompt 1	DA ($attr'_1 = val'_1, \dots, attr'_m = val'_m$) + s	DA ($attr_1 = val_1, \dots, attr_n = val_n$)
Prompt 2	DA ($attr''_1 = val''_1, \dots, attr''_n = val''_n$) + s'	DA ($attr_1 = val_1, \dots, attr_n = val_n$)
Prompt 3	DA ($attr_1 = val''_1, \dots, attr_n = val''_n$) + s''	DA ($attr_1 = val_1, \dots, attr_n = val_n$)

Table 4: Task demonstrators of a real Input MR from the English EMPATHIC corpus. Similarly to Table 3, the DA in blue and attributes (in this case only 'action') in red highlight that they are identical in the Task demonstrator and the MR input. Contrastingly, demonstrator attributes in violet highlight those that differ from the input attributes.

Input MR	RQ_curr_sit (action = eat)
Prompt 1 demonstrator	RQ_curr_sit (action = tell; freq = daily) + Can you tell me about your daily eating habits?
Prompt 2 demonstrator	RQ_curr_sit (food = water) + And do you think you drink enough water?
Prompt 3 demonstrator	RQ_curr_sit (action = change) + Would you like to change your eating habits?

demonstrators of Prompt 2 and Prompt 3 match the number of attributes with the baseline input, 1. In addition, the attribute of Prompt 3 is the same as the input MR, i.e., action. Therefore, the table depicts the different levels of specificity of the three proposed representations.

4 Experiments

The cross-lingual experiments that we present in this section follow the methodologies proposed in (Vázquez and Torres, 2025) by using the same setup and evaluation metrics but adding new language models for non-English languages.

4.1 Experimental framework

For the validation of the proposed representations, we fine-tuned GPT-2 models (Radford et al., 2019) for each pair of representation and language. In particular, we chose GPT-2 Medium for English and three versions of the GPT-2 Small for the other three languages: MarIA (Gutiérrez-Fandiño et al., 2022) for Spanish, BelGPT-2 (Louis, 2020) for French and Norwegian GPT-2 social² for Norwegian.

These fine-tuning experiments included 5-fold cross-validation. The byte-pair tokenizer was the same as in the pre-training (Sennrich et al., 2016). We performed over five training epochs using a learning rate scheduler with a linear warm-up that starts 5e-5, an Adam optimizer with weight decay (Kingma and Ba, 2014), and a batch size of 8. In the generation phase, we produce five sentences per MR, constrained to a maximum length of 80

tokens. We set the temperature to 1.0 in order to obtain more variable outputs.

4.2 Metrics

Table 5 describes the five evaluation metrics employed in this work. This evaluation covers different aspects of the generations. First, it includes widely-used metrics such as (BLEU) (Papineni et al., 2002) and Slot Accuracy (Li et al., 2020). Next, BERT models (Devlin et al., 2019) are employed to evaluate the semantics with different approaches for BLEURT (Sellam et al., 2020) and LaBSE (Feng et al., 2022). Finally, we include Dialogue Act Accuracy (DAC), an underexplored metric that evaluates the accuracy of classifiers to predict the source DA of a generated sentence. Thus, it measures the coherence of the generations with the DA intent given in the MR input.

4.3 Automatic evaluation

Table 6a and Figure 2 of the Appendix A present the results for the fine-tuned models and the metric evolutions, respectively. Both show that the models fine-tuned with the prompts perform better than Baseline models according to the five metrics. In addition, the more specific the task demonstrator is, the higher the benefit is: Prompt 3 is the best Prompt representation. In this regard, there are some exceptions for English and French models for DAC, where Prompt 1 outperforms the others. In these cases, we guess that even if generation can be worse, the source DA could be more easily identifiable. In fact, these particular models obtain the lowest Slot Accuracy values within the same language, which indicates more omissions in these

²<https://hf.rst.im/pere/norwegian-gpt2-social>

Table 5: Metrics description.

Metric	Evaluated aspect	Reference	Methodology to obtain the score
BLEU	Lexic	Corpus sentences for same Input MR	BLEU-4 with a smoothing function (Chen and Cherry, 2014)
BLEURT	Semantic	Corpus sentences with the same Input MR	BERT model trained with human ratings for similarity of pair of sentences
LaBSE	Semantic	Corpus sentences with the same Input MR	Cosine similarity between BERT embeddings of generations and references
Slot Accuracy	Semantic	MR Input (focused on the values)	Percentage of values of the MR Input in the generated sentence
DAC	Communicative intent	MR Input (focused on the DA)	F1-score with DistilBERT models (Sanh, 2019) as DA classifiers

Table 6: Metric scores for each combination of metric (*Metri*), language (*Lang*) and representation. In the languages, *en*, *es*, *fr* and *no* stand for English, Spanish, French and Norwegian. For the representations, *Base* is the Baseline representation, P_i refers to Prompt i representations and *Val* is the Validation score for DAC. Evolution of the metric scores epoch by epoch can be found in Figure 2 of Appendix A.

(a) After fine-tuning

Metri	BLEU				BLEURT				LaBSE				Slot Accuracy				Dialog Act Accuracy				
	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	Val	Base	P1	P2	P3
en	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.26	0.54	0.56	0.57	0.60	0.66	0.67	0.68	0.70	0.88	0.86	0.87	0.90	0.68	0.65	0.71	0.69	0.69
es	0.11	0.13	0.15	0.22	0.41	0.45	0.47	0.53	0.59	0.63	0.64	0.67	0.70	0.69	0.70	0.78	0.66	0.53	0.68	0.65	0.68
fr	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.21	0.34	0.36	0.37	0.44	0.64	0.67	0.67	0.70	0.71	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.68	0.54	0.67	0.62	0.65
no	0.10	0.12	0.13	0.20	0.42	0.46	0.47	0.51	0.64	0.67	0.67	0.69	0.66	0.69	0.69	0.75	0.66	0.52	0.61	0.61	0.64

(b) Zero shot-settings

Metri	BLEU				BLEURT				LaBSE				Slot Accuracy				Dialog Act Accuracy				
	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	Base	P1	P2	P3	
en	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.22	0.27	0.27	0.28	0.20	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.38	0.50	0.52	0.61	0.03	0.21	0.20	0.19	
es	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.09	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.22	0.21	0.20	0.19	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	
fr	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.35	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	
no	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	

generations. Finally, the improvement with the enriched inputs is more evident and similar between them in all the non-English models. Then, the demonstrators seem to be more relevant in small models.

The zero-shot capabilities of the prompt representations may also be affected by the model. Table 6b and Figure 2 show that these MRs improve Baseline results before training in English for all the metrics except for BLEU. However, this behavior does not appear in the non-English target languages. We can assume that the difference with English resides in the GPT-2 models: Medium for English and Small versions for the other languages. A bigger size and more adequate pre-training for dialogue tasks in the Medium version can result in better generations in zero-shot settings.

The metric analysis validates some of our findings about them from (Vázquez and Torres, 2025). Comparing the very low BLEU results (principally after fine-tuning) with all the other metrics, we confirm its low reliability in evaluating the generation quality. At the semantic level, BLEURT presents bigger differences in its values across languages after fine-tuning than LaBSE. BLEURT, trained with human ratings, tends to detect omissions/hallucinations that LaBSE, based on sentence embeddings, does not. This assumption is sup-

ported by slot accuracy, a metric to evaluate the percentage of omission. The behavior of this metric follows the same tendency as BLEURT. Finally, DAC, with results very close to the validation values, evidences the robustness of the models to generate coherent sentences with the expected communicative intention.

4.4 Qualitative evaluation

Table 7 shows examples of generations for four different MRs. For each example, the table provides the MR, the language, the references, the training setup (fine-tuned or zero-shot), and up to three generations for each representation. These generations are selected and ordered in the table according to the average value over all the metrics except the DAC³. We confirm that the specificity of the prompts is more relevant with complex inputs (first example of the Table) and in non-English languages (third example). In these cases, Prompt 3 is the only one that always produces at least one adequate sentence. For simpler inputs (second example), the most basic prompts are effective in producing good generation, even for MR inputs in which the Baseline is not.

For zero-shot settings like the last example

³The DAC has been excluded because it is a classification metric that only assigns values of 1 and 0 to each generation.

Table 7: Generation examples. Each example contains the MR, the language, the references from the original corpus, the training setup (fine-tuned or zero-shot), and up to three generations for each representation (Baseline, Prompt 1, Prompt 2, and Prompt 3). These generations are selected and ordered according to the average value over all the metrics except DAC, since it only assigns 1 and 0 scores as a classification metric. <no_sense_seq> stands for sequences with no sense.

MR Input	Int_travel_quest (action = do ; freq = each time)	Language	English
References	- Do you have something you like to do each time you go on vacation? - Is there something you like to do each time you go on vacation?	Training setup	Fine-tuned
Baseline	- And do you do it to do it each time? - For each trip, do you do it differently? - Do you do it each time?		
Prompt 1	- Can you tell me about the to-do for each time? - To do each time? Each time you do it, what's the objective?		
Prompt 2	- Can you tell me about your to-do for a specific date or every time? -Do you do it each time? - Can you tell me about your to-do?		
Prompt 3	- Do you have something you like to do each time you go on vacation? - And do you have something you like to do each time you go on vacation? - Each time you go on vacation?		
MR Input	Gen_Yes_no_quest (food = fish)	Language	English
References	- Do you eat fish?	Training setup	Fine-tuned
Baseline	- And fish? - And eat more fish?		
Prompt 1	- What about fish? - So you like fish, right? And fish?		
Prompt 2	- Do you eat fish? - What about fish? - And eat fish?		
Prompt 3	- Do you eat fish? - And do you eat fish? - And fish?		
MR Input	Int_viajes_comentario (acción = imagina ; acción = decir)	Language	Spanish
References	- Como puede imaginar, no viajo mucho. Sólo puedo escuchar lo que tienes que decir.	Training setup	Fine-tuned
Baseline	- ¿Y crees que tienes un objetivo muy claro en el viaje de qué te ha motivado? - ¿Te gustaría ir a un sitio que te gustaría contar? - ¿Con qué frecuencia sueles hablar con sueles afectarte?		
Prompt 1	- Estoy aprendiendo a decir. Me interesa especialmente la música y los viajes. - Tengo que contar esto.		
Prompt 2	- Imagina ¿y por qué te gusta viajar? - Imagina ¿sueles viajar con otra persona? - Imagina		
Prompt 3	- Como puede imaginar, no viajo mucho. Sólo puedo escuchar lo que tienes que decir. - Como puede imaginar, no viajo mucho.		
MR Input	RQ_curr_sit (food = fruits ; food = vegetables ; freq = a day ; numbers = five)	Language	English
References	Do you eat five fruits and vegetables a day?	Training setup	Zero-shot
Baseline	- <no_sense_seq> - <no_sense_seq> - <no_sense_seq>		
Prompt 1	- <no_sense_seq> - <no_sense_seq> - <no_sense_seq>		
Prompt 2	- <no_sense_seq> - <no_sense_seq> - <no_sense_seq>		
Prompt 3	- <no_sense_seq> Do you eat five fruits and vegetables a day? <no_sense_seq> - Do you eat five vegetables a day? - <no_sense_seq>		

of the table, most of the generations contain sequences with no sense⁴. Nonetheless, Prompt 3 often presents good generations. Note that these good outcomes are identified by the metrics, as we can observe in the generations for Prompt 3 in the table. However, among these generations, "<no_sense_seq> Do you eat five fruits and vegetables a day? <no_sense_seq>" has been identified as the best sentence instead of "Do you eat five vegetables a day?". This situation can be resolved by adding an LLM perplexity to our metrics to discard all the generations that include these kinds of sequences. All in all, despite these undesired sequences in most generations, we consider the results promising for extending the zero-shot generation approach with prompt inputs to larger LLMs such as GPT-3.5 (Brown et al., 2020) and LLaMA (Touvron et al., 2023), which have shown strong performance in prompt-based tasks.

5 Conclusions

This work explored how prompt-based inputs can enhance natural language generation in cross-

lingual, coaching-oriented dialogue systems. These tasks are particularly complex due to their need for controlled, semantically rich outputs that support user reflection, often in low-resource language settings and with diverse dialogue act taxonomies. Our results show that increasing the similarity between the demonstrator and the input meaning representation improves both coherence and accuracy, especially when using smaller pre-trained models. These findings suggest that prompting strategies can meaningfully improve generation quality in highly structured, goal-driven dialogues. Future directions include testing prompt transferability across languages and domains, and integrating such strategies into real-time interactive systems.

⁴We denote these sequences as <no_sense_seq>.

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A Fine-tuning evolution

Figure 2: Evolution of the average score of each metric during the fine-tuning with each representation for each language. *Slot Acc.* stands for Slot Accuracy and *Norw.* for Norwegian. In the DAC results, there is a dotted line for Validation results.